

Whole genome sequences of *Colletotrichum siamense* and *Colletotrichum truncatum*, causal agents of pod and foliar diseases on African yam bean

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Running head: WGS of *Colletotrichum* spp. from African yam bean

Keywords: pod blight, foliar disease, African yam bean, *Sphenostylis stenocarpa*, illumina, *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides* species complex.

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Abstract

Diseases caused by *Colletotrichum* fungi result in major agricultural losses worldwide. Here, we present two draft genomes of *Colletotrichum* spp. responsible for foliar disease and pod blight on the orphan-legume African yam bean. *Colletotrichum siamense* and *Colletotrichum truncatum* assemblies totalled 55.8 Mb in 563 contigs and 54.8 Mb in 1240 contigs, respectively.

Announcement

The genus *Colletotrichum* is composed of a diverse group of destructive plant pathogenic fungi causing rots, blights and dieback disease across a wide range of host plants including legumes, fruits, vegetables, ornamentals and trees (1). This genus is organised into species complexes which comprise a diverse array of genetic and phenotypic traits (2). Of these, *Colletotrichum siamense*, which belongs to the *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides* complex, was first reported infecting coffee in Thailand and later in many other crops across tropical and sub tropical regions (2). In contrast, *Colletotrichum truncatum* has been documented as the predominant causal agent of anthracnose in pepper (3) and soybean (4). In soybean production, *C. truncatum*

has been reported to cause yield losses of up to 26% in the United States of America, 50% in Thailand, and 100% in India (5).

Colletotrichum species also affect important subsistence crops such as African yam bean (AYB; *Sphenostylis stenocarpa*). In one study, Afolabi et al. (6) reported anthracnose symptoms in 100% of the sampled AYB flower buds and pods. Based on a multilocus phylogenetic analysis (ITS, GAPDH, ApMAT and CAL) we recently demonstrated *C. truncatum* and three species belonging to the *C. gloeosporioides* species complex, including *C. siamense*, to be responsible for AYB leaf tip dieback, pod blight, and flower bud rot diseases (7). These diseases threaten cultivation of AYB in most growing areas of Nigeria. Potential tissue specialisation was observed between these species, with *C. siamense* being the most prevalent fungus associated with leaf tip dieback disease whereas *C. truncatum* was the predominant causal agent of AYB flower bud rot and pod blight diseases (7). Given the economic importance of *C. truncatum* and *C. siamense* in crop production, expansion of genomic resources will improve the ability to study plant-fungal species adaptation and tissue-specific adaptation, and will support molecular genetics of plant-microbe interactions to identify bases of crop resistance.

Two isolates of *Colletotrichum* species associated with AYB diseases were sequenced in the current study: *C. siamense* S2L1F3, for leaf disease, and *C. truncatum* Pod6, for pod blight. The fungal isolates were grown on potato dextrose agar medium and, after 7 days, the mycelium was inoculated into 20 ml of potato dextrose broth (Sigma-Aldrich, Missouri, USA) and incubated at 24°C for 5 days. Cultures were filtered using filter paper (Whatman, Gillingham, Dorset) and washed twice using sterile distilled water (dH₂O). The mycelium was then frozen in liquid nitrogen and ground into a fine powder.

The genomic DNA of S2L1F3 and Pod6 were extracted using the protocol of Carter-House et al. (8). Illumina library preparation and sequencing of these isolates was carried out by

MicrobesNG (Birmingham, UK; microbesng.com) using the manufacturer's protocols with the following modifications: input DNA quantity was doubled and the PCR elongation step was increased to 45 s. DNA quantification and library preparation were carried out on the Hamilton Microlab STAR liquid handling system (Hamilton Bonaduz AG, Domat/Ems, Switzerland). Libraries were sequenced on an Illumina NovaSeq 6000 (Illumina, San Diego, USA) using 250 bp paired end sequencing (Birmingham, UK; microbesng.com). Resulting reads were trimmed using Trimmomatic v.0.30 with a sliding quality cutoff of Q15 (9). *De novo* sequence assemblages were performed using SPAdes v.3.7 (10). Within the *C. truncatum* and *C. siamense* assemblies, approximately 0.20% and 0.004% of the total bps, respectively, were identified as putative contaminants by the NCBI contamination screen and were removed from the draft genome. Final assembly quality was assessed using Quast v.5.2 (11) and genome completeness assessed using BUSCO v.5.7.0 (12) to identify presence, completeness and duplication of 3817 single-copy genes from the sordariomycetes_odb10 dataset.

The size of assembled *C. siamense* S2L1F3 and *C. truncatum* Pod6 genomes was 55.8 Mb and 54.8 Mb in 563 and 1240 contigs and N50s of 506.6 kb and 161.9 kb, respectively (Table 1). Mean read coverage was determined to be 57.84 and 69.47 for these genomes, respectively. Assembly of the core genome was determined to be near-complete, with over 98% of 3817 conserved single-copy Sordariomycete genes found to be present in a single copy within both assemblies, with minimal duplication (Table 1). The GC content of the genome was 52.92% and 48.98% for *C. siamense* and *C. truncatum*, respectively. The presented assembly statistics are in-line with current publicly available genomes for these taxa: the current reference genome (NCBI-RefSeq) for *C. truncatum* is 56.1 Mb in size with an N50 of 831.7 kb (13). The genome of *C. siamense* is smaller than the current 62.94 Mb NCBI RefSeq (14) but in-line with an unpublished 56.82 chromosome-level assembly for this species (Accession#ASM3802388v1).

The genomic resources generated in this project provide new tools to study *Colletotrichum* diversity, host adaptation, and genome evolution within this pair of species and across the wider genus. In particular, the consistent association of these species with two distinct tissues of AYB provides opportunities to investigate the genetic basis of tissue-specific host adaptation of two closely related fungi (7), in a crop with limited genetic study of plant-pathogen interactions.

The whole genome shotgun sequencing project has been deposited at DDBJ/ENA/GenBank under the accession numbers GCA_031008025.1 for *C. truncatum* and GCA_031009615.1 and for *C. siamense*.

Acknowledgement

We acknowledge the assistance of GetGenome and The Sainsbury Laboratory, Norwich, UK, for generating the whole genome sequence data of the *Colletotrichum* species, supported by Gatsby Charitable Foundation and the Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council (BBSRC). Olaide Ogunsanya acknowledges financial support from a Commonwealth Split-Site PhD Scholarship. Andrew Armitage acknowledges financial support from the BBSRC Expanding Excellence in England award: Food and Nutrition Security Initiative in Africa.

Table 1: Summary statistics of genome assemblies of *C. siamense* and *C. truncatum* isolated from African Yam Bean (AYB) leaf and pod material. Presence of 3,817 Benchmarking Universal Single Copy Orthologous (BUSCO) genes were used to assess assembly completeness.

Fungal species	<i>C. siamense</i>	<i>C. truncatum</i>
Strain	S2L1F3	POD6
Source material	AYB leaf	AYB pod
Source location	5.8702 N 8.5988 E	7.3775 N 3.9470 E
Total contigs	563	1,240
Total length (bp)	55,831,030	54,793,555
Largest contig (bp)	1,366,400	705,093
GC content (%)	52.92	48.98
N50 (bp)	506,610	161,938
% BUSCO groups identified	99.7	99.7
% BUSCO complete & single copy	98.1	98.2
% BUSCO complete & duplicated	0.3	0.2
Biosample	SAMN33312890	SAMN33312889
WGS project	JARSS01	JARSS01
Genbank accession	GCA_031009615.1	GCA_031008025.1

References

1. Silva C, Michereff, S. 2014. Biology of *Colletotrichum* spp. and epidemiology of the anthracnose in tropical fruit trees. *Revista Caatinga*. 26. 130-138.
2. Weir BS, Johnston PR, Damm U. 2012. The *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides* species complex. *Studies in Mycology*. 73:115–180.
3. Liu F, Wang M, Damm U, Pedro WC, Cai L. 2016. Species boundaries in plant pathogenic fungi: a *Colletotrichum* case study. *BMC Evol Biol* 16: 81.
4. Rogério F, Ciampi-Guillardi M, Barbieri MCG, Bragança CAD, Seixas CDS, Almeida AMR, Massola Jnr, NS. 2017. Phylogeny and variability of *Colletotrichum truncatum* associated with soybean anthracnose in Brazil. *Journal of Applied Microbiology*. 122, 402–415.
5. Hartman GL, Sinclair JB, Rupe JC. 1999. *Compendium of Soybean Diseases*, 4th ed.; APS Press: St. Paul, MN, USA.
6. Afolabi C, Ogunsanya OM, Isiaq, L. 2019. Evaluation of some African yam bean (*Sphenostylis stenocarpa* [Hochst. Ex A. Rich]) accessions for resistance to flower bud and pod rot diseases. *Current Plant Biology*. 20. 100126. 10.1016/j.cpb.2019.100126.
7. Ogunsanya OM, Adebisi MA, Popoola MA, Afolabi CG, Oyatomi O, Colgan R, Armitage AD, Thompson EP, Abberton M, Ortega-Beltran A. 2024. Morphological, pathological, and phylogenetic analyses identify a diverse group of *Colletotrichum* spp. causing leaf, pod, and flower diseases on the orphan legume African yam bean. *bioRxiv*. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.04.03.587868>

8. Carter-House D, Stajich J, Unruh S, Kurbessoian T. 2020. Fungal CTAB DNA Extraction v1. 10.17504/protocols.io.bhx8j7rw.
9. Bolger AM, Lohse M, Usadel, B. 2014. Trimmomatic: a flexible trimmer for Illumina sequence data. *Bioinformatics* 30(15):2114–2120.
10. Bankevich A, Nurk S, Antipov D, Gurevich AA, Dvorkin M, Kulikov AS, Pevzner PA. 2012. SPAdes: A new genome assembly algorithm and its applications to single-cell sequencing. *J. Comput. Biol* 19(5), 455–477.
11. Alexey G, Vladislav S, Nikolay V, Glenn T. 2013. QUASt: quality assessment tool for genome assemblies, *Bioinformatics* 29 (8): 1072-1075.
12. Manni M, Berkeley MR, Seppy M, Zdobnov EM. 2021. BUSCO: assessing genomic data quality and beyond. *Current Protocols*, 1(12), e323.
13. Flávia R, Thaís RB, Maisa C, Serenella AS, Michael RT, Nelson S, Massola Junior NS, Riccardo B. 2020. Genome sequence resources of *Colletotrichum truncatum*, *C. plurivorum*, *C. musicola*, and *C. sojiae*: four species pathogenic to soybean (*Glycine max*). *Phytopathology*. 110:9, 1497-1499
14. Becerra S, Baroncelli R, Boufleur TR, Sukno SA, Thon MR. Chromosome-level analysis of the *Colletotrichum graminicola* genome reveals the unique characteristics of core and minichromosomes. 2023. *Front Microbiol*. 14:1129319. doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2023.1129319.